

D8.1

Dissemination and Communication Plan

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List of abbreviations

Table 1. List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Term
Diss & Comm	Dissemination and Communication
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
ROI	Return of Investment
LEC	Local Energy Communities
VC	Validation Cases
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
EU	European Union
TA	Target Audiences
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
AI	Artificial Intelligence
UX	User Experience
DSO	Distribution System Operator
TSO	Transmission System Operator
EU	European Union
LECs	Local Energy Communities
RES	Renewable Energies Sources
WP	Work Package
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

1. Introduction

Project Summary

A greener energy system is crucial for the future prosperity and liveability of European citizens. This requirement is at the heart of the DATA CELLAR approach where Local Energy Communities (LECs) have been recognised by the European Commission as a pivotal measure to play a key role in driving the EU's energy transition. At the same time, the digitisation of the EU energy system and the proper exchange of data between energy actors appear crucial to foster the exchange of best practices and the creation of a knowledge community to tackle one of our society's most pressing global crises: climate change.

Figure 1. Project explanation

In this context, DATA CELLAR aims to implement a collaborative platform that will provide an interoperable, and secure energy data space capable of delivering access to datasets and AI models to serve and support the spread of energy communities in the European Union, leveraging on experience gained in the development of other EU projects.

DATA CELLAR will create a decentralized data space to store streams or historical data coming from private metering, but it will also provide a data federation integrating data coming from both external companies and EU federation spaces. The data space will be populated by a series of services dedicated to energy utilities, energy communities, private businesses, and citizens. Furthermore, DATA CELLAR will provide a decentralized and open marketplace for energy datasets and pre-trained AI models to serve and support LECs. To achieve its objectives, DATA CELLAR is divided into 9 WPs with different objectives, tasks and deliverables.

2. Executive Summary

“DATA CELLAR aims to create a public energy data space that will support the creation, development and management of Local Energy Communities (LEC) in the EU”

DATA CELLAR (“**Data Hub for the Creation of Energy communities at Local Level to Advance Research on them**”) is an initiative funded by Horizon Europe programme by the European Commission, with the objective of establishing the grounds for a common European energy data space. The project is based on the idea of the global need of a greener energy system. The transformation will not only tackle new forms of technologies, but will require a great digital development. These will create a vast amount of new data, as already foreseen by the most recent EU policy directives, that will serve new ways of understanding business, reducing costs or increasing efficiency.

This hyper-connected scenario has made organisations realise the value of the data they were gathering and, are paving the way to the creation of data spaces where information can be sold, traded or exchanged. In fact, EU data economy, increased from 1.94% of the GDP in 2015, to the 4% in 2020. Not only that, estimations say that the volume of data will increase 530% by 2025.

The **European Strategy for Data** aims to create a single data market to support Europe’s competitiveness and sovereignty, thus allowing public spaces and businesses across Europe, to exchange data in a trustworthy and cost-effective way, based on five “gold standards”: 1) *Environmental sustainability*; 2) *Data Protection*; 3) *Digital Identity*; 4) *Cybersecurity* and 5) *Interoperability*.

DATA CELLAR aims to develop a dynamic, interoperable energy-oriented data platform to support the uptake of energy communities leveraging a blockchain-based tokenization scheme for the remuneration in data and pre-trained AI models provisioning cycle. Project objectives are the following:

- **Development, validation and demonstration of a dynamic data hub ensuring continuously updated, reliable and credible data.** This means, to ensure interoperability using open standards, protocols and data models; ensuring the high quality of data with the use of AI methods for analytics and implement the distributed and federated data space and edge-cloud management for scalability.

- **Implement privacy and cybersecurity-by-design measures according to GDPR and national data handling regulations and security standards.** In this regard, special attention will be given to the storage of personal data that can reveal a user's behaviour and to the cybersecurity measures at different levels to ensure a trusted environment for all participants.
- **Provide access to AI models and data-driven energy services by making use of the stored and exchanged data, supporting the energy transition.** DATA CELLAR will provide a complete data analysis framework, which will support the services of the next-gen LEC oriented energy management and planning.
- **Create and sustain a highly engaged data sharing ecosystem of EC data providers (Energy Utilities, DSOs, Aggregators single Prosumers) through a DLT-based open marketplace,** with the creation of an innovative incentive scheme. This token-based economy will, thus empower a user-centric, data-driven economy.
- **Evaluate DATA CELLAR novel business models upon real Energy Community use cases and collaboration with other relevant EU on-going initiatives participating in BRIDGE to facilitate interoperability testing and demonstration,** facilitating data federation and removing data silos at an EU scale.

DATA CELLAR initiative gathers **31 partners from 15 countries** (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Portugal, Spain, Switzerland, The Netherlands, United Kingdom). The types of organisations cover the full value chain needed for the success of this project, namely: research organisations, private entities, non-profit organisations, public bodies and education establishments.

The partners in the consortium are:

- **RINA CONSULTING SPA.** Italy (*PROJECT COORDINATOR. Leader of WP1, WP7 & WP9*)
- **ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS.** Greece (*Leader of WP2*)
- **FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS.** Spain
- **UBITECH ENERGY.** Belgium. (*Leader of WP5*)
- **NODES AS.** Norway
- **POLITECNICO DI TORINO.** Italy.
- **QUE TECHNOLOGIES KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA.** Greece. (*Leader of WP4*)

- **AZIENDA ELETTRICA DI MASSAGNO (AEM) SA.** Switzerland.
- **FONDAZIONE LINKS - LEADING INNOVATION & KNOWLEDGE FOR SOCIETY.** Italy (*Leader of WP6*)
- **FUNDACION CTIC CENTRO TECNOLOGICO PARA EL DESARROLLO EN ASTURIAS DE LAS TECNOLOGIAS DE LA INFORMACION.** Spain
- **COMMISSARIAT A L ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVES.** France
- **CNET CENTRE FOR NEW ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES SA.** Portugal
- **CEZ DISTRIBUTION BULGARIA AD.** Bulgaria
- **YUGOIZTOCHNOEVROPEYSKA TEHNOLOGICHNA KOMPANIA OOD.** Bulgaria
- **IREN SPA.** Italy
- **IREN MERCATO SPA.** Italy
- **IREN ENERGIA SPA.** Italy
- **ELECTRICITE DE FRANCE.** France
- **EUNICE ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES GMBH & CO. KG.** Germany
- **TRILATERAL RESEARCH LIMITED.** Ireland
- **TRILATERAL RESEARCH LTD.** United Kingdom
- **RIJKSUNIVERSITEIT GRONINGEN.** The Netherlands
- **ZABALA BRUSSELS.** Belgium (*Leader of WP8*)
- **ZABALA INNOVATION CONSULTING, S.A..** Spain
- **EPL Technology Frontiers Limited.** Cyprus
- **UNIVERSITY OF CYPRUS.** Cyprus (*Leader of WP3*)
- **AUSTRIACARD AG.** Austria
- **EMAC EMPRESA MUNICIPAL DE AMBIENTE DE CASCAIS EM SA.** Portugal
- **COMHARCHUMANN FUINNIMH OILEAIN ARANN TEORANTA.** Ireland
- **NOORD-HOLLAND.** The Netherlands
- **FUNDACION ASTURIANA DE LA ENERGIA.** Spain

3. Objectives of the Dissemination & Communication plan

Europe's future energy policy increasingly relies on innovative solutions that allow to provide energy to consumers in a clean, secure and affordable way. Taking this into account, the role of communication in innovation should aim to demonstrate how the European Union adds value on research and provide tangible results that can be recognised by the citizens.

In this regard, the Clean Energy Package approved by the European Union in 2018, admits citizens to have an active role in the development of the EU energy system, in particular, to benefit from the possibilities offered by the sector of the renewable energies sources (RES). This will also allow to accomplish the collective objectives set by the EU, which are: a share in the consumption of at least 27% coming from RES by 2030, and the full decarbonisation of the electricity is expected by 2050.

To meet these challenging targets, by 2050, half of the EU citizens are expected to produce their own electricity supplies, thus giving Energy Communities a critical role in the energy transition. DATA CELLAR will aim to integrate the data coming from different operators within the energy communities (DSOs, aggregators, LEC managers, etc.) interweaved with the energy and climate mechanisms' requirements.

The objective of **DATA CELLAR Dissemination and Communication Plan** is to use the results generated during the project to create an added value for the target audience of the project that could be extrapolated to a wider EU public, ensuring the accountability of the adequate use of public funds for the optimal positioning of the European stakeholders globally.

To summarise, the project will raise awareness of the project and its results for external audiences, also promoting the knowledge within the targeted audiences:

- **Promotion of the clean digital technologies** as a climate and environmental sustainability enablers (following UN SDGs) that foster the efficient use of energy and resources which, at the same time, also has an impact on social and economic aspects.
- **Promotion of European Energy Communities.** As already mentioned, citizens are expected to become one of the main pillars of energy transition and, as such, have a substantial influence in the energy

market, which will not be limited to the electricity supply, but will bring transversal societal transformations.

Communication, dissemination and exploitation aim to maximise the impact of the research actions. The differences among them concentrate on the objectives, focus and audiences. The strategy explained in this document contains all three as a cross-cutting line of action of DATA CELLAR.

Figure 2. Communication master

Figure 3. Main differences between Diss & Comm

The Plan will consist of three phases that will run successively along the project timeline:

- **Phase 1 (M1-M15):** Create visibility around the project, its Validation Cases (VC), the participating partners and data space benefits.
- **Phase 2 (M16-M36):** Disseminate the results oriented for exploitation purposes once the dataspace will be running.
- **Phase 3 (M28- M48):** promotion of the overall results to be used beyond the project timeframe stimulating the replication and engagement of future investors and participants.

The **DATA CELLAR Communication Master Plan** will combine online and offline channels and activities creating a comprehensive approach to all objectives and stakeholders, that will reinforce the messages.

Figure 4. Dissemination and Communication

4. Target audience

A good identification of the target audiences (TA) is of the utmost importance of any communication strategy. It serves to adapt the ideas and activities to the interests and behavioral traits of each group of people. The **DATA CELLAR Communication Master Plan** will then shape the messages and its way of delivering them according to the public.

Partners will have an important role, as they will be asked to provide their networks, identify networking opportunities and perform specific activities that will enhance the impact of the project. Said otherwise, the coordination among WP leaders and demonstrators foreseen during the project will be key for the dissemination and communication at local levels, while promoting the involvement of third-parties in the design of the methodologies beyond the project. At the proposal stage, the following stakeholders were identified, with influence at a European, national and local levels:

- **Energy Communities (Phase 1, 2, 3):** the benefit will be the unlock of the possibilities of flexibility to improve network operation, which will directly impact revenue through the reduction of energy costs and impact on the grid, and consequently, the reduction of CO2 emissions. *Examples: energy community managers, operators and aggregators.*
- **Energy Utilities (Phase 1, 2, 3):** These include power plant managers and data providers. These TAs will also benefit from the possibilities of interoperability that DATA CELLAR will unlock. *Examples: DSO/TSO, grid operators, power plant managers and data providers*
- **ICT/AI/ Data Analytics Developers (Phase 1, 2, 3):** They will be crucial in the DATA CELLAR ecosystem as facilitators and developers of the interface adaptation of the dataspace. *Examples: ICT and AI developers and data analysis experts.*
- **Scientific Community (Phase 1, 2, 3)** will be greatly benefitted from DATA CELLAR through the exchange of data and services, thus enabling the development of other innovative solutions. *Examples: Universities and research centres.*
- **EC Platforms (Phase 2, 3):** DATA CELLAR will seek collaboration with other EU communities and projects creating synergies among stakeholders. *Examples: ETIP SNET, BRIDGE.*
- **Policymakers (Phase 2, 3):** The development of the features of the dataspace will only be possible with the collaboration of multiple entities, including the public sector. *Examples: European Commission, European Parliament, national governments and its ministries, local authorities.*

- **Media (Phase 1, 2, 3):** The role of the media will be the awareness raising and knowledge transfer to specialised and general society. *Examples: media outlets and specialised journalists.*
- **End-users (Phase 3):** Energy data will be considered a common good allowing energy systems to function in a more optimised way. The mutual collaboration among the TAs above finalising with the end-user will ensure that the project has a greater impact in the ecosystem at several levels (research, economic, environmental and societal). *Examples: energy consumers, prosumers (current and potential).*

4.1. Key Dissemination and Communication channels and activities

DATA CELLAR Communication Master Plan has chosen the channels, tools and materials outlined below for the dissemination and communication strategy of DATA CELLAR:

Table 2. Channels, tools and materials for Diss & Comm

Dissemination & communication tools/ actions	Description
Visual Identity and guidelines	Professional logo, visual guidelines and DATA CELLAR templates to be used in the communications and outcomes related to the project.
DATA CELLAR website	The website will host information about the project, its pilots, validation cases, results and news related to DATA CELLAR topics. Positioning services and valuable materials uploaded to the “Downloads area”, will ensure that it becomes a useful communication channel for all internal and external stakeholders.
Multimedia products	Audiovisual material will be produced and shared in social media channels and events. In the framework of DATA CELLAR, two videos are expected to be produced: the first, presenting the project’s objectives and, a second one, detailing the lessons learnt and the use of the dataspace.
Newsletters/ targeted mailings	An electronic quarterly newsletter will be sent with the latest news about the status of the project, its developments and related news. In addition, targeted mailing actions will be distributed in key moments, such as the participation in events or the dissemination of press releases.
Social Media	DATA CELLAR aims to create a community around energy communities. Social Media channels are an excellent mean that allows general audiences to be in a close contact with relevant stakeholders, such as the public sector. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Twitter will serve to be up to date about general news and a direct communication with TAs. • Linkedin aims to a more specialised and professional

	<p>audiences. The community sought will be more engaged here.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youtube will host our project videos about the features of the project as well as the trainings.
Contact with media: articles, interviews and media presentations	<p>Due to the newsworthy value of the project, it will attract the attention from media. DATA CELLAR will seek the contact of specialist and generalist media outlets alike that will help us spread and multiply the results across the TAs. Partners will be requested to support these actions within their areas of influence (geographic and thematic).</p>
Networking with similar initiatives	<p>DATA CELLAR will seek synergies with similar sister initiatives which involve related stakeholders and communities related to data spaces. Among the most relevant, we will seek liaison with BRIDGE, GAIA-X and ETIP SNET, that will enable the dissemination the results at a policy -makers’ level while gathering very relevant insights at the same time.</p>
Events and training workshops	<p>Education sessions will be one of the core activities of DATA CELLAR that will hit the throttle in PHASE 2, once the exploitation-oriented results will be mature enough. In addition to the aforementioned collaboration with sister dataspace initiatives, the project also plans to develop a full training plan in partnership with universities, thus giving access to valuable scientific audiences.</p>
Other communication materials	<p>A promotional toolkit of DATA CELLAR will be created to be used during events in order to advertise the visual identity and raise awareness. It will include the following materials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DATA CELLAR brochure • DATA CELLAR flyer • DATA CELLAR poster • DATA CELLAR roll-up

5. Communication tools and actions

5.1. DATA CELLAR Brand

The first communication action within DATA CELLAR was to create a recognisable and attractive brand for the project. The visual identity reflects the main goals of the initiative, showing a distinctive image for the public.

DATA CELLAR means: “*DATA hub for the Creation of Energy communities at Local Level and to Advance Research on them*”. The full title should be included in brackets when it is mentioned for the first time in a document then, the acronym will be the preferred option. In addition, when using the abbreviation, unless otherwise agreed for a particular reason, it will always appear in capital letters.

Figure 5. DATA CELLAR Visual identity

5.1.1. Logo and visual guidelines

DATA CELLAR aims to create a public energy dataspace that will support the creation, development, and management of LECs (Local Energy communities) in EU. DATA CELLAR will implement a collaborative platform providing an interoperable, modular, and secure energy data space capable of delivering access to datasets, Decision Support Tool, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) models to serve and support the spread LECs.

This means that the brand revolves around two big brand concepts:

ENERGY

The brand has one main theme, **energy**. Create a database where energy forms are shared between communities. This energy flows, connects between different people and becomes, as these ideas generate new ones. This is also characterised in the brand. Linear forms, which generate movement and continuous transformation and which connect with each other.

PEOPLE

People are the ones who share and receive the information, a project made for knowledge and the increase of new practices in the face of energy. The logo generated for everyone, where there are no lower or upper case letters that define the tone or the information of the brand. It is characterised by being legible, dynamic and approachable

Figure 6. Big brand concepts

Taking into account the previous, we development of the visual identity can be summarised as follows:

PEOPLE	ENERGY	CONNECTIONS

Figure 7. Brand concepts visual identity

A visual guideline showing the appropriate uses of the DATA CELLAR logo and colours has been developed:

The DATA CELLAR isologotype:

Figure 8. DATA CELLAR isologotype

The DATA CELLAR isotype:

Figure 9. DATA CELLAR isotype

The DATA CELLAR typography:

Aa

PLUS JAKARTA SANS

Secondary typography is a combination of legibility and dynamism. It can be used both for paragraph text and to support headlines and graphic elements.

Aa

BARLOW

Main typeface used for brand headlines, this typeface can be used both online and offline. It is a dry stick typeface that appears to have a condensed appearance. This will allow you to create standout headlines with ease and create a contrast with the logo and secondary typeface.

Aa

Figure 10. DATA CELLAR typography

The DATA CELLAR colour palette:

SECONDARY COLOURS

GRADIENTS COLOURS

Figure 11. DATA CELLAR colour palette

To summarise, the correct use of all the previous (logotype, isotype and colour palette) would be along these lines:

Figure 12. DATA CELLAR colour correct use

5.2. Digital Marketing Strategy

As we mentioned, the main objective of DATA CELLAR is to establish and feed European energy communities around the defined TAs and third-party stakeholders. For this reason, we could establish three big unavoidable lines of action:

- DATA CELLAR website will be continuously updated, in particular the news and events sections.
- Social Media platforms and newsletters will be used to share the developments about the project and attract visitors and users to the website.
- SEO techniques will be applied to improve the performance and positioning on Google.

In addition, the project will seek to establish synergies and collaboration among the consortium partners, which includes the feedback among their online channels. The following table compiles the partners' website addresses and social media platforms:

Table 3. Partners' website and social media channels

PARTNER ORGANISATION	Website	Twitter	LinkedIn
RINA Consulting	https://www.rina.org/en	@RINA1861	RINA
CERTH	https://www.certh.gr/	@CERTHellas	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH)
CIRCE	https://www.fcirce.es/	@fCIRCE	CIRCE - Centro Tecnológico
UBITECH	https://energy.ubitech.eu/	@Ubitechenergy	UBITECH ENERGY
Nodes	https://nodesmarket.com/	-	NODESMarket
QUE TECHNOLOGIES KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA	https://www.que-tech.com/	@QueTechnologies	Que Technologies
Politecnico di Torino	https://www.polito.it/	@PoliTOnews	Politecnico di Torino
AZIENDA ELETTRICA DI MASSAGNO (AEM) SA	https://aemsa.ch/it	@AEMInfo	Azienda Elettrica di Massagno (AEM) SA
Fondazione Links	https://linksfoundation.com/	@LinksFoundation	LINKS Foundation – Leading Innovation & Knowledge for Society
CTIC	https://www.fundacionctic.org/	@fundacionctic	CTIC Centro Tecnológico

CEA	https://www.cea.fr/	@CEA_Officiel	CEA
EDP	https://www.edpr.com/	@EdpRenewables	EDP
CEZ DISTRIBUTION BULGARIA AD		-	-
YUGOIZTOCHNOEVROPEYS KA TEHNOLOGICHNA KOMPANIA OOD		-	-
IREN SPA	https://www.gruppoiren.it/	@gruppoiren	Gruppo Iren
EDF		-	-
EUNICE	https://eunice-group.com/	-	Eunice Energy Group
Trilateral Research	https://trilateralresearch.com/	@TRIResearch_	Trilateral Research
RUG	https://www.rug.nl/	@univgroningen	Rijksuniversiteit Groningen
Zabala Innovation	https://www.zabala.eu/	@zabala_eu	Zabala Innovation Europe
EPL Technology	https://www.epl-technology.com/	-	-
University of Cyprus	http://www.pvtechnology.ucy.ac.cy/	@UCYOfficial	PV Technology, FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy
AUSTRIACARD	https://www.austriacard.com/	-	AUSTRIACARD
EMAC		-	-
COMHARCHUMANN FUINNIMH OILEAIN ARANN TEORANTA	https://www.aranislandsenergycoop.ie/	@CfloatArainn	-
NOORD-HOLLAND		-	-
FAEN	https://www.faen.es/	@FundacionFaen	Fundación Asturiana de la Energía, FAEN

5.2.1. Website

The DATA CELLAR website is now created and available from M4 (September 2022). The website is the main Dissemination and Communication tool of the project and will also include project materials to download as well as showcase the results.

The website will act as the media hub for DATA CELLAR project. It will connect all technical stakeholders at local, national and European level, media outlets and general audience in the same spot. All online and

offline activities will be duly reflected here, thus attracting visitors to the site. The sections are the following:

- General information about the project.
- Description of all the organizations members of the consortium.
- Information, objectives, work packages and validation cases
- Information about participation in surveys and the training programme
- Reporting of the participation in events
- Press releases and media package
- Newsletters
- Public deliverables
- News items
- Contact information
- EU funding acknowledgement disclaimer

Responsive design. DATA CELLAR website will be multidevice, that is: the website will be correctly displayed in all kinds of portable devices. A good web adapted to mobile gadgets improves the user experience (also called UX), thus reducing the bound rate. What is more, having a responsive design is very relevant for the ranking in search engines. For example, Google, facing two websites with a similar SEO value, will give preference to the one better adapted to mobile devices.

Keyword optimisation: the content of the website will have several keywords inserted regularly on the text and design modules, which will help us generate traffic through search. Some of the keywords proposed are:

- *Data*
- *Energy communities*
- *Energy transition*
- *Resource efficiency*
- *Data Space*
- *Local Energy Communities*
- *Innovation*
- *Flexibility*
- *Validation case*
- *Token system*
- *Public Energy*
- *AI models*
- *Energy consumers*
- *Energy prosumers*
- *DSO*
- *TSO*
- *LECs*
- *Collaborative platform*

Content organisation follows UX and readability rules, also taking into account EU guidelines and best practices. A good user experience directly translated to more session time and returns to the webpage.

Content feed: in order to avoid being penalised by search engines, it is important to be constant and publish regularly. A good option to keep the website active is by the promotion of it in the rest of our channels, thus building links to the content. Google will then recognise it as a relevant and interesting.

Figure 13. Website main screen

5.2.2. Newsletter and mailing actions

A quarterly newsletter will be shared via Mailchimp. A registration form will be created in that platform, posted in the website and promoted through social media, that will feed the database. The preliminary contact list will be created thanks to the partners' networks. Needless to say, contact databases will strictly comply with GDPR regulation.

The newsletter will be fed from website news and provide the links there, that way, recipients will also visit the website. The design will follow DATA CELLAR visual identity. Once the newsletter has been sent, partners will promote it via their organisations' channels. Newsletters will also be shared via stakeholders' associations and uploaded in the website in a dedicated tab section.

5.2.3. Social media platforms

The creation of a community around DATA CELLAR is vital for the maximisation of brand’s and results’ visibility of the project. LinkedIn and Twitter will be the platforms used for Social Media strategies that will end up in the backing up of the website. In addition, Youtube will be the chosen platform to host the project videos (promotional and training-wise) from DATA CELLAR.

Social Media accounts have been set in M1 (June 2022) by ZABALA, who will also lead the management of them. Nevertheless, the support of the communication responsables of the partner organisations is expected to reach out more local audiences and foster online conversation.

Full details of the partners’ social media platforms are detailed in section 5.2.

TWITTER: @DATACELLAR_EU

Twitter will offers a good opportunity for DATA CELLAR to connect with diverse target audiences, with a special interest on international sphere (European Commission, policy makers, industry, local and national authorities, similar initiatives, general interested audience). Twitter will be the platform used for real-time communication during events. In order to improve the presence, the use of some hashtags will be promoted:

#DataCellar	#DataSpace	#DSO	#HorizonEurope
#DATACELLAR	#Data	#TSO	#EnergyTransition
#DATACELLAR_EU	#LocalEnergyCommunities	#EUProjects	#Sustainability
#Energy	#PublicDataSpace	#Innovation	#ResourceEfficiency
#EnergyCommunities	#TokenSystem	#LECs	#Flexibility
#RenewableEnergy	#AIModels	#EUFunding	#ValidationCase
#PublicEnergy	#EnergyConsumers	#EnergyProsumers	#CollaborativePlatform

Figure 14. DATA CELLAR Twitter profile

LINKEDIN: DATA CELLAR EU

LinkedIn is nowadays the main business network in the world. DATA CELLAR stakeholders are mostly in this platform and, even if many people look at it from a job seeking perspective, it is the most meaningful one for engagement. Said otherwise, a LinkedIn company page will enable DATA CELLAR be seen as a professional and reliable project.

LinkedIn allows the dissemination of products for slower consumption, i.e. content that can be consumed at a leisurely pace, like: presentations, blog posts, infographics, embedded videos, etc. It will be seen as an adjacent complement to the webpage in content, but its role, in addition to the community engagement, will be to redirect visitors to our main hub.

Figure 15. DATA CELLAR LinkedIn profile

YOUTUBE: DATA CELLAR EU

Youtube channel will serve to share DATA CELLAR promotional videos and recoding of the trainings. The main objective will be to complement the influence of Twitter and LinkedIn, by the feedback across the platforms. Multimedia content (videos in particular), create deeper engagement rates in visitors, thus strengthening the dissemination and communication strategy.

Figure 16. DATA CELLAR social media networks and website workflows

5.3. Supporting Communication materials

A series of communication and dissemination materials will be developed in order to effectively translate DATA CELLAR messages and raise awareness. These will be of the utmost importance, for instance, during events. All the following items will be available in an online format and be shared in DATA CELLAR online working environment.

- **DATA CELLAR presentation** (Powerpoint) in English including of the project’s description, objectives and expected results will be prepared. It will be completed and validated by the partners of the consortium.
- **DATA CELLAR roll-up** will contain the main information in order to be used in events and conferences along the whole project timeline.

- **DATA CELLAR brochure & flyers** will also be produced. Similarly, they will contain the project's most important information to be versatile for all kinds of events. If necessary, targeted flyers can be produced for key events.

5.4. Media relations

DATA CELLAR will seek the contact of specialist and generalist media outlets alike that will help us spread and multiply the results across the TAs. Media relations will be led by ZABALA as WP leader, however all partners will be requested to support these actions within their areas of influence (geographic and thematic), and as a general way, with the following:

ZABALA will prepare the press release in English after the key moment. Once the press release is approved by the Communication Team, every partner will translate it into their local language and will send it to their press and stakeholder contacts.

Next, the partner will further promote the press release on their communication channels, which could be (not limited to) their websites, Social Media platforms and newsletter

After that, impacts and coverage will be monitored and informed to ZABALA, who will include those in the reports and website

In addition to the previous, DATA CELLAR will make use of other distribution platforms such as CORDIS WIRE to ensure a greater dissemination of the content. As mentioned, press releases will take place in key moments of the project, which will coincide with the development of the project, its results and milestones:

- Identification and presentation to sister projects of the preliminary workflow and DATA CELLAR architecture.
- Manual of guidelines to share data on DATA CELLAR.
- First version of DATA CELLAR DSS and data driven services/AI libraries.
- Creation and animation of a data provider/developers community fostered by a token-based rewarding system.
- Final event & presentation of the policy paper.
- DATA CELLAR beyond project strategy after the exploitation workshop.

Other opportunities to share press releases could be:

- Participation in events (own or organised by others).
- General assemblies of the project.
- Launch of DATA CELLAR videos.
- Key takeaways from trainings.

In order to serve as a database to proceed with when preparing specialised content on the project, here is a table with the main general and specialised media with which we can work to achieve greater dissemination of the project results.

Table 4. Media outlet

Name	Type of media
EFE	Generalist
Europa Press	Generalist
Data Center Dynamics	Specialised
DPA (Agencia de Noticias Internacional)	Generalist
Artenergy publishing	Specialised
Zeroemission	Specialised
El País	Generalist
El Mundo	Generalist
La Vanguardia	Generalist
El confidencial	Generalist
ABC	Generalist
Photovoltaics International	Specialist
Energías Renovables – Renewable Energy Magazine	Specialist
Energy Harvesting Journal	Specialist
Energy Now	Specialist
Energy Industry Times	Specialist
Environmental Data Interactive Exchange	Specialist
Green Energy Observer	Specialist
Industrie et Technologies	Specialist

Renewable Energy Focus	Specialist
New Energy	Specialist
Energías Renovables	Specialist
Energy News	Specialist
Energy Post	Specialist

5.5. Events

The participation in events – International conferences, congresses, webinars- is a key part of Diss & Comm. The objectives of the attendance and organisation of events are the following:

Figure 17. Objectives of events

The industry partners will demonstrate the benefits of DATA CELLAR project and will analyse potential systems among other actors in energy industry for booting the commercialisation after the end of the project.

During the project implementation, events will be organised to foster stakeholder engagement, including with local politicians, the energy industry, and the general public.

The main results will be introduced in the market through the participation in EU events, webinars and cooperation actions listed below. This list is preliminary and will be continuously updated with new events throughout the project's life cycle:

Table 5. Upcoming events

Name	Location	Date
Spark Conference	London (UK)	Junio-22
ENLIT Europe	Frankfurt (France)	29/11/2022 - 01/12/2022
EUSEW 2022	Brussels (Belgium)	Sept-22
Cybersecurity for energy & Transport infrastructure	Genova (Italy)	8-9/11/2022
Smart City ExpoWorlds Congress	Barcelona (Spain)	15-17/11/2022
Gaia-X summit	Paris (France)	17-18/11/2022
European Big Data Value Forum	Prague (Czech republic)	21-23/11/2022
IEEE International Conference on Big Data	Osaka (Japan)	17-20/12/2022
Citizens Energy Congress	Not defined	Not defined
IoT Week	Berlin (Germany)	June 2023
CIREN International Conference on Electricity Distribution	Not defined	17-20/06/2023
Intersolar Europe	München (Germany)	13-16/06/2023

The project will also organise its own DATA CELLAR events, sometimes in collaboration with other initiatives. All events will be promoted through social media and the website of the project. When attending an event, the partners should inform to the Communication team in advance in order to prepare the necessary materials or campaigns in social media.

Procedures for events:

The workshops and trainings sessions are directed to energy professionals and researchers, students, industry, policymakers and Media.

To maximise their impact, some steps will be followed:

- A background briefing document will be sent to participants before the events.
- Event materials will be published online and distributed to participants and partners. When attending an event, the partners should inform the Communication team in advance to prepare the necessary materials or campaigns in social media.
- A report will be generated by each partner leading the event, summarizing the event and the recommendations made by experts.

5.6. Networking

Specific activities will be done to reinforce the positioning of the project and foster the cooperation with relevant ongoing initiatives, such as liaising with relevant EU and national institutions clustering with ongoing national and or international research and innovation activities. During the project, a common framework will be established for the dissemination of the project results covering all communities involved in order to be better positioned in a number of EU initiatives.

DATA CELLAR consortia will use the experience gained in different projects and interaction with different regulatory agencies to networking with other projects and initiatives, because of their previous relations.

5.6.1. Specific initiatives related to the project

GAIA-X

GAIA-X aims to create a federated open data infrastructure based on European values regarding data and cloud sovereignty. It will develop a data sharing architecture that includes common standards for data sharing, best practices, tools and governance mechanisms.

DATA CELLAR will provide feedback and foster collaboration with GAIA-X, where the representatives from business, science and politics on an international level are creating a proposal for the next generation of data infrastructure.

OPEN-DEI

OPEN-DEI is a EU-funded project that fosters the creation of common data platforms based on a unified architecture and an established standard in manufacturing, agriculture, energy, and healthcare.

In the context of manufacturing, OPEN DEI creates an agile value network, promotes excellence, enhances the human factor and stimulates the sustainability value network. Via OPEN DEI, dynamic solutions can be exploited for designing customized products, while Industry 4.0 concept is promoted by zero defect manufacturing from data driven products and services. Additionally, a view in the future workplaces is demonstrated by humans and autonomous systems collaboration. Finally, OPEN DEI promotes the application of circular economy principles to the manufacturing process.

OPEN DEI contribution to the energy sector occurs in allowing exchanges among market players (e.g., aggregators, consumers/prosumers, etc.), assisting the energy systems integration according to market information updates, while enhancing the physical system infrastructure (e.g., generation, conversion, storage, networks) according to consumers requirements. Finally, OPEN DEI facilitates the digital input of energy sector, delivering higher levels of automation.

In regard of influencing the agriculture sector, OPEN DEI creates a trusted environment for new technologies, establishes standards for data management and information exchange, and creates a validation interoperability solution among platforms and information systems.

In the domain of healthcare, OPEN DEI promotes cybersecurity for big data, innovations associated with AI and robotics are encouraged via testing beds and IoT.

DATA CELLAR will establish collaboration and knowledge exchange with the OPEN DEI project focused on “Platforms and Pilots” to support the implementation of next generation digital platforms in industrial/energy domains.

PANTERA

PANTERA is an EU H2020 project aimed at setting up a European forum composed of Research & Innovation stakeholders active in the fields of smart grids, storage and local energy systems, including policy makers, standardisation bodies and experts in both research and academia, representing the EU energy system.

This meeting point will allow to share results and strategies fostering the innovation strategies for the sector. Furthermore, DATA CELLAR will take advantage of PANTERA training/knowledge sharing opportunities to both promote the project and collect relevant datasets for the dataspace.

5.6.2. Interaction with BRIDGE

BRIDGE is a European Commission initiative which unites Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe Smart Grid, Energy Storage, Islands, and Digitalisation Projects to create a structured view of cross-cutting issues which are encountered in the demonstration projects and may constitute an obstacle to innovation. The BRIDGE process fosters continuous knowledge sharing amongst projects thus allowing them to deliver conclusions and recommendations about the future exploitation of the project results, with a single voice, through four different Working Groups representing the main areas of interest.

BRIDGE initiative will allow to share the knowledge generated delivering conclusions and recommendations about the future exploitation of the results, through the four BRIDGE working groups: data management, business models, regulations, and consumer and citizen engagement.

For DATA CELLAR, the more interesting Working group is the one focused on Data Management, which is working on:

- Communication infrastructure, embracing the technical and non-technical aspects of the communication infrastructure needed to exchange data and the related requirements, including issues faced by TSO and DSO.
- Cybersecurity and Data Privacy, entailing data integrity, customer privacy and protection.
- Data Handling, including the framework for data exchange and related roles and responsibilities, together with the technical issues supporting the exchange of data in a secure and interoperable manner, and the data analytics techniques for data processing.

To increase the impact of DATA CELLAR we can put it in contact with projects and initiatives that can help create synergies to grow as a project. In addition, given that Zabala Innovation is the coordinator of the secretariat, it can be used to activate coordination mechanisms with other projects to have their contact to ask for collaboration in events, workshops, or information sessions that are considered necessary.

5.7. Scientific publications

It is expected that DATA CELLAR develops a significant amount of research results which will be disseminated to different key scientific communities (scientific conferences and peer-reviewed and and

international specialised magazines). Thus, research and academic partners will dedicate strong efforts in publishing scientific papers under the framework of global recognized scientific conferences and journals that count on high impact index due to their specialism.

All the research outputs will be aligned with the Open Access and Open Science regulations of EU. More specifically, the publications of the project will be published in Open Access Journals which will be initially checked from the platform and DOAJ and Open Access Repositories (i.e. Zenodo). In order to succeed the optimum level of impact along with the most cost-efficient method, the involved researchers will utilize both Green Open Access (selfarchiving in open repositories) and Gold Open Access (peer reviewed publications in open access journals or/and repositories) strategies according to the content of the outputs.

Material produced by project partners must follow the review and approval procedure should follow the guidelines below:

- Are asked to follow the corporate identity of DATA CELLAR.
- Should include in the communication materials produced the EU flag with the disclaimer.
- Ensure the accuracy of the information by always consulting the Description of Action.
- Use available material previously approved (whenever possible).
- Send ZABALA a copy of the published document and press clippings in order to keep track of all the dissemination activities.
- Provide their contact details at the end of their presentations, articles and press releases, but also share ZABALA contact details.

5.8. Campaigns and replication tools

The strategy will be organised in three main phases, which are:

- **Phase I focusing on raising interest among stakeholders (M1-M15).**

Here the project must show visibility about the project, Validation Cases, data space benefits via interesting raising activities and distribution of public dissemination materials. It will be an opening event to launch project preliminary results, inviting representatives for other dataspace funded sister projects.

- **Phase II focusing on the exploitation-oriented dissemination of results (M18-M36).**

DATA CELLAR must demonstrate its benefits once the dataspace will be running. Here the activities included are publications of papers and articles in journals and relevant conferences, workshops and events. And here the training plan will start.

- **Phase III focusing on the promotion of the overall results beyond the project (M28-M42).**

DATA CELLAR will stimulate the replication of the concept and the engagement of potential future clients. The results of the project will be promoted during a final event in Brussels also helpful to collect Stakeholders' final insights.

To achieve all the objectives and raise awareness about the project with dissemination, the campaigns will be divided into three groups: events, trainings, and validation cases.

5.8.1. Events

As explained before, in 5.5 the participation at events is a key point for communication and dissemination of the project. When the procedures that has been explained are assumed, the next step will be to prepare the campaign by Zabala team.

There are three types of events in which we can group them: organising, attending and interesting.

Organising events: Events in which DATA CELLAR as a project itself organise and decide who to invite, how to host the meeting (if onsite or online), the agenda, the speaker, etc. At the moment there are three events at a glance. The first one will be the second fortnight of October 2022, in which DATA CELLAR will present some validation cases of partners, one technical approach and give time for questions about the project. Another one will be held more or less at the middle of the project to inform to our stakeholders how the project is being developed, some results that can be published and maybe next steps that we are going to work on. An the third one is the final event in Brussels the last month of the project that will show all our results and collect the stakeholders' final insights.

Attending events: These type of events are the ones in which we assist like partipants, or speakers. At a glance we have with short deadline the EUSEW (Europeam Sustainable Energy Week), from 25 to 29 of September, and an event with other dataspaces the 30th of September. Furthermore, POLITO and RUG will

promote DATA CELLAR in their Energy and Electric Engineering courses, also inviting as speakers relevant project partners, and the must organise at least 4 webinars per year on DATA CELLAR topics.

Interesting events: These events are the ones that some partner detect and think that is a good idea someone to attend it, just to clarify doubts about one term, or to find some synergies with other projects or to do useful networking with other organisations or initiatives.

Events procedure

Whenever DATA CELLAR is going to be present at an event, whether as an organiser, participant or spectator, its participation and interest must be communicated through the project channels. When participating or organising the event, a specific notice will be written on the website announcing the participation, explaining why you are going to participate, what the contribution will be and how to access the event (in case it is online or with unlimited capacity).

In addition, when DATA CELLAR is the organiser, there will be a post-event news item in which the main conclusions, with a short summary of what has been the presentation, will be told. And in case it can be published because all the speakers give their consent, the recording of the event will be added to the news for later consultation.

However, when the event is only attended as a spectator because some interest has been detected, the communication will be less, simply by social networks confirming attendance at the event and attaching a photograph as far as possible to show the more human side of the project, the people who are working to make it go ahead.

5.8.2. Trainings

Due to the great and good experience of FOSS and EDP in building training programmes for the promotion of LECs, they will be in charge of organising the successive training that is contemplated in the proposal throughout the development of the project.

Although they will design the training plan, spend time creating content, inviting the best experts, and finding the best focus for the sessions, it will be Zabala Innovation as the leader of the communication

package who will be in charge of guaranteeing the success of these training, or at least the attendance, thanks to its communication and dissemination work.

A total of at least 10 web-training sessions and 6 physical sessions (1 more EU oriented in concomitance with project final event and 5 privileging the VCs areas and countries also to use native language) all along the project lifetime is foreseen, under FOSS-EPL coordination and with the support of DATA CELLAR key developers, VCs representatives, etc. as speakers and for training material preparation.

Trainings procedure

When one of the training organised by DATA CELLAR is going to take place, Zabala Innovation as communication leader will lead the Digital Marketing strategy to promote the event, always with the collaboration and support of the rest of the partners, who must contribute to the promotion from their channels to reach a greater number of people.

For the online sessions, which are more numerous than the face-to-face sessions, ZABALA will prepare a standard poster that will vary according to the basic information of the event (date, time, and name), which will be distributed among its partners. Thus, on the one hand, the project will communicate the holding of the training, with a news item on the website and a campaign on social networks. On the other hand, each partner will be able to communicate it through its channels (web and social networks, if possible), to reach a wider audience and make it accessible to everyone interested.

For the promotion of the project, two news items will be prepared: one before the event announcing it, and a post-event one with the main conclusions and lessons learned. And the same process will be done on social networks, although if possible, and if there is no overlapping content, the event will be promoted with at least 3 posts explaining the main points and announcing the event as the date gets closer and closer. And for the promotion in the partners' channels, the news announcing the event will be sent to all of them so that they can adapt it to their websites and communicate it openly and completely. Two posts will also be prepared so that they can publish them on their social networks reacting to the official posts uploaded on the project's profiles.

For the face-to-face training, the procedure on the web and social media will be the same as for the online training, but in addition, specific materials will have to be prepared and made available to the attendees. A roll-up will be designed and produced where pictures will be taken to publish about the event so that

people can send them to their communication departments and complete leaflets presenting the project will be distributed and people can take them back to their companies to discuss it with more colleagues.

5.8.3. Validation Cases

The DATA CELLAR data space will be validated in 9 Validation Case which represents different Energy community at different level of maturity in terms of status of the energy community. The Validation Cases represents a wide range of possible energy communities that could be found around Europe and are managed/promoted by different stakeholders. The Validation Cases will interact at two different levels with DATA CELLAR:

- **PROVIDE DATA:** Crowd the data space with existing data around energy communities which will cover different energy (electricity, heating and cooling, gas, water...) and non-energy vectors (mobility, transport, user behaviours...).
- **DRIVE BUSINESS:** The different stakeholders through the data space, will have access to both data to be used in an aggregated way for their business as well as the different data-driven services that will be developed eithin DATA CELLAR and that will be available to the stakeholders.

VCs procedure

The project will carry out 9 cases of validation that already have their own section explaining them on the website. This facilitates communications, as each time one occurs, a news item will be published on the website that will be shared with the partners and disseminated on social networks, but it will also include all the detailed information in the specific section of the website so that stakeholders can find out about it in the simplest way possible.

It will be communicated using a combination of the technical language that researchers and end users of validation cases are used to, but also trying to bring it down to the simplest level so that anyone a little specialised in the subject can understand what is being announced and communicated there.

5.9. Specific Diss & Comm actions per WP

Table 6. Diss & Comm actions per WP

Task	Title	Goal	What Diss & Comm must do	Lead
T1.1	Users and Market Needs Characterization via a participatory approach	The goal of this task is to identify the needs of the most relevant users of the data space through the support of VCs and technical partners and consortium members which are engaged in existing databases. This will be conducted, together with external stakeholders, through a Design Thinking approach (survey and workshops to be organised with the support of RINA-C and ZABALA).	It will be necessary to organise several workshops with the support of RINA.	EDP
T1.2	Requirements for Data Governance and Data Interoperability among different Data Spaces and Data Provision from existing monitoring from VCs	The output of this task will be a set of data governance/data interoperability requirements/guidelines to be respected by DATA CELLAR Data Space to be shared with T1.3.	As a result of the guidelines that arise from the task, our job will be to create a news item to publish on the website.	CTIC
T1.3	DATA CELLAR preliminary requirements and specifications	To guarantee a proper integration with the other EU Data Spaces (existing and funded under this call for proposal – with latest ones as specific joint workshop presenting D1.4 will be organised in collaboration with WP3) as well as with the European Commission strategies for the creation of a common overarching EU dataspace.	A workshop should be organised presenting the D1.3 "DATA CELLAR preliminary requirements and specifications and project KPI/Monitoring strategy".	QUE
T1.4	Definition of KPIs for the project monitoring and evaluation plan development	This task, led by RINA-C as project coordinator, aims to define a set of KPIs to evaluate the effectiveness of the DATA CELLAR in terms of: 1) QUALITY OF DATA CELLAR and USERS' SATISFACTION; 2) IMPACT ON	We must prepare content for the web.	RINA-C

		VALIDATION CASES; 3) IMPACT ON EU ENERGY COMMUNITY; 4) IMPACT ON EU DATASPACE CREATION AND ANIMATION.		
D1.1	DATA CELLAR potential users' wishes and needs collected via a participatory approach also for LEC self-assessment tool development	WP1, Lead by EDP, PUBLIC, M6	Prepare a news item for the website announcing that the deliverable has been published.	EDP
M1	Organization of a survey and EU Stakeholders' workshop to collect wishes and needs for DATA CELLAR	WP1, Lead by EDP, M3, Survey properly filled-in at least by 30 stakeholders	Support in the organisation of the workshop to be led by EDP.	EDP
M2	Identification and presentation to sisters' projects of the preliminary work-flow and DATA CELLAR Architecture	WP1, Lead by QUE, M9, Preliminary requirements and specifications agreed between sister projects'	Communicate to the project stakeholders who the sister projects are.	QUE
T2.1	Data-set and Data Streams Identification for DATA CELLAR: What, Why, Where, How and Types	This task aims to make an inventory of relevant energy/non-energy data to identify what data shall be collected, why are they necessary, the data source and how it can be collected through for example voluntary metering schemes or interaction with local energy operators.	A summary will be prepared for publication on the website.	POLITO
T2.2	Data Generation, Acquisition and Ingestion	This task will analyse the available techniques to gather and provide energy data, respectively to populate DATA CELLAR data space and identify how the end-users can obtain and use these data.	We will publish an article on the website explaining what will be the purpose of the existing data collection.	LINKS
T2.3	Interaction Schemes among Data Provider, Data MarketPlace, Data Broker and Data Consumers	This task aims to analyse and clarify the interaction schemes among the components involved in the exchange. The primary objective is to define and clarify the governance schemes between the different entities involved, such as data providers.	Once the interaction systems and governance schemes are known, it would be a good idea to	LINKS

			write an article.	
T2.4	Data Anonymization and Aggregation Schemes	This task will identify the strategies, guidelines, and potential common algorithms/approaches to aggregate and anonymize data particularly from VCs. The objective is to exclude unnecessary information while keeping high quality and meaningful data even through strong aggregations.	An article will be published on the website explaining how the GDPR influences the project.	CERTH
T2.6	Guidelines about ethics aspects on data handling for DATA CELLAR	In order to ensure that all users and data providers consider the ethical considerations regarding dealing with data from the cellar, this task will develop several guidelines, protocols and policies.	Through a web article, it will be explained that protocols and policies have been developed.	TRI
D2.3	Guidelines, protocols and policy on legal and ethical aspects for fair data handling	WP2, Lead by RUG, PUBLIC, M15	Prepare a news item for the website announcing that the deliverable has been published.	RUG
T3.1	Assesment of relevant existing EU databases and how to interconnect to them and the other ENERGY Dataspace	Identification of other existing EU databases or dataspace and identification of their primary goals and identification of the major data sets which can be provided to populate the DATA CELLAR and/or which data set can be provided from our DATA CELLAR (in collaboration with T1.1).	Explain the databases of European projects with certain similarities to our project.	UBE
T3.4	Validation of DATA CELLAR in other project validation cases	In order to guarantee funded project/data space interaction, this task will promote the use of DATA CELLAR dataspace among VCs of other projects funded under the same EU call and vice versa. The final goal of this task is to prove the openness, usability and effectiveness of DATA CELLAR dataspace.	We will publicly communicate the interaction with the other projects under the same call.	CTIC
T4.1	Data Model (DM) to support the DATA CELLAR infrastructure	This task will cover the development of the DATA CELLAR Data Model (DM) to match the particular project requirements to organize elements of data and standardize how they relate to one another and	A release will explain the procedures that have been followed during the	LINKS

		the properties of real-world entities.	development of the project.	
T4.3	Overall reference Architecture Design through Open standards related to data-packages, interfaces, protocols, platforms and procedures	This task aims to define and design the Platform Architecture (see Section 1.2) along with the (Open) standards which will be used for the interconnection of the various modules/components. To achieve this, a UML workflow will be followed.	We will explain using a notice on the web what will be the architecture of the project.	QUE
T4.5	Interfacing of DC-CDE with external components	This task aims to design and develop the components of the DC-CDE that interface with external components, either to ingest data from numerous sources or to deliver data to the DATA CELLAR value-adding services.	It could increase knowledge about the project by explaining in a news item how interactions between the project and external components occur.	QUE
M7	DATA CELLAR Beta Version tested by VCs and feedback collected for final release	WP4, Lead by QUE, M30, List of improvements from VCs have been collected from all the VCs responsible	Communicate the development of the VCs on the website.	QUE
T5.1	Artificial intelligence and Machine Learning libraries for ad-hoc data analysis for Energy Communities	The main aim of this task is to develop a set of AI libraries for processing the data gathered in the DATA CELLAR by exploiting innovative AI techniques.	We should explain how a set of libraries is developed by an article.	LINKS
T5.4	DATA CELLAR Dashboard and HMI	This task will deal with the development of the DATA CELLAR HMI, which shall be user-friendly and easy to handle, allowing convenient data scouting through a dashboard and data upload/sharing, as well as the HMIs of the DSS and other relevant components that will require user interaction.	We should explain how an HMI works, how it is easy to use, and how it is convenient to browse.	CERTH
D5.1	AI models and libraries for	WP5, Lead by LINKS, PUBLIC, M27	Prepare a news item for	LINKS

	energy communities also including modules on algorithmic transparency and explainability		the website announcing that the deliverable has been published.	
D5.2	Digital Twin based on DATACELLAR Data for Energy Communities developers	WP5, Lead by UBE, PUBLIC, M27	Prepare a news item for the website announcing that the deliverable has been published.	UBE
D5.3	DATA CELLAR users' interaction: HMI and DSS for energy communities' developers	WP5, Lead by CIRCE. PUBLIC, M42	Prepare a news item for the website announcing that the deliverable has been published.	CIRCE
T6.1	Modelling, Packaging, Deployment and onboarding of new libraries in the marketplace	This task aims at developing a tool to allow energy data analysts to design, develop and release new and advanced algorithms and models for the extraction of meaningful and valuable insights from energy datasets. This task shall also provide a scheme for new users to upload (onboarding) new libraries with private or public schemes. The user experience will be a key element of this development environment and will be mainly based on a user-centric visual approach that will enable also non-expert users to create and run a data analysis pipeline through the combination of pre-loaded building blocks (algorithmic block and data blocks).	We should publish content explaining the developed tool (how it will work in the future), so that when the user enters for the first time, he/she has a base to start from.	LINKS
T6.2	Interoperable, low energy consumption DLT layer	The main objective of this task is to choose which DLT platform best fits the needs of DATA CELLAR in terms of scalability and data security, while providing a decentralised and open marketplace for data and models. Taking into account the interoperability and federation needs for EU Energy Data Spaces, focusing on low-energy consensus	Explain why the chosen DLT platform has been chosen, its advantages and disadvantages, how it works...	LINKS

		algorithms.		
T6.3	Governance and transaction models for trusted and secured private metering	This task aims to design and implement an open market for data and AI models using blockchain technology. The information can be registered in a tamper-proof manner along with their origin (or identity) in order to guarantee a "Proof-of-Origin".	Explain in an expert article what blockchain technology is and how it will be used in the project.	LINKS
T6.5	Marketplace Integration and Orchestration also considering management of workspaces	This task is in charge of the integration of the Marketplace made of the libraries, Digital Twins and DSS and other outputs developed in WP5, as well as the components developed in WP6 for the business scenario data evaluation, library onboarding, etc., on top the cloud platform where the data streams will be stored or retrieved from other dataspace. The Marketplace will enable end-users of DATA CELLAR to gain access to the outputs of the project, such as the AI model training software, data sharing software, or resources and infrastructure management. The Marketplace will allow DATA CELLAR to offer its services using several business models (subscription, free to use, etc.) as defined by the DATA CELLAR consortium.	The existence of the Marketplace shall be communicated as well as the developed components that serve to evaluate the data.	AC
D6.1	Energy Data Analytics Visual Tool	WP6, Lead by LINKS, PUBLIC, M18	Prepare a news item for the website announcing that the deliverable has been published.	LINKS
D6.2	DLT Architecture and Governance Model	WP6, Lead by LINKS, PUBLIC, M18-36	Prepare a news item for the website announcing that the deliverable has been published.	LINKS
D6.3	Token-based Incentive Schema and Marketplace Components Integration	WP6, Lead by LINKS, PUBLIC, M39	Prepare a news item for the website announcing that the deliverable has	AC

			been published.	
M10	Creation and animation of a dataproviders/developers community fostered by a token-based rewarding system	WP6, Leady by LINKS, M33, Token-based rewarding model defined and agreed between partners	Through communication on the website, clarify questions about what a token-based reward model is.	LINKS
T7.2	Energy Scenarios creation via DATA CELLAR to study the impact of energy communities in EU energy system	In this task, a “Higher-level” validation case will be developed by EDF, that will use data coming from DATA CELLAR to develop EU Energy scenarios to investigate (also thanks to lessons learnt from VCs) which will be the impact of Energy Communities on EU Energy system and grids towards 2030-2050.	Organise an event (on-site/online) to explain the chosen Higher-level VC.	EDF
T7.3	Lesson Learnt and Best Practices also to engage new data provider and energy communities stakeholders	Building on the results of T7.1.1, this task aims to collect lessons learned from the validation campaign to understand the ease of data integration, acceptability of data sharing, etc., to attract future data providers and users for DATA CELLAR, also assessing how DATA CELLAR is expected to influence the creation of future energy communities. Interviews will be conducted with each VC partner and integrated with lessons learned into a final project handbook, incorporating also the perceptions of the energy community managers.	The handbook including the interviews with each VC partner will be presented and the lessons learned therein will be summarised.	EDP
T7.6	Exploitation strategy of DATA CELLAR and of project results	The aim of this task is to define how to exploit project results in a mutual way among partners as well as respecting IPR. All partners directly involved in “Key parts” of DATA CELLAR will be involved in order to understand how they intend to act after project end to guarantee a long-lifetime of DATA CELLAR as well the market/R&D	Support the exploitation strategy at all times by disseminating key messages explaining the results and implementing actions.	RINA-C
D7.2	Eu Energy Scenarios and role of energy communities	WP7, Lead by EDF, PU, M42	Prepare a news item for the website announcing	EDF

	investigated thanks to DATA CELLAR		that the deliverable has been published.	
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6. KPI’s and monitoring

Analytics are an essential source of information for measuring the impact of Communication and Dissemination actions. Monitoring and analytics will be incorporated in DATA CELLAR Communications strategy in order to analyse and measure the Return of Investment (ROI) in communications.

Zabala Innovation will coordinate the actions related to measuring of the communication activities, with the collaboration of all the partners in the project. The analytics will be incorporated on the DATA CELLAR website, social media, and other communication processes as a source of essential information for monitoring key indicators (KPIs).

Each member of the consortium, which make use of the communication tools and channels, must provide feedback about the impact achieved with their efforts. This information is essential to test and update the strategy and to fill the D8.3 Reporting on Dissemination and Communication/Training/EU initiatives Interaction Activities in the month 21 and 42 of the project.

The Communication strategy will be under constant review to monitor and adapt actions, as well as having feedback to maximise impact for published content (interviews, articles and videos) and the entire dissemination strategy. The indicators will be systematically analysed and shared in all dissemination updates and project meetings.

To keep track of the evolution of the Communication Strategy, the following Key Performance Indicators (KPI’s) will be considered:

6.1. Communication Performance Indicators

Table 7. KPI's

Communication tools	KPI	Expected impact
Website	Socio-demographic data studies of the website visitors	5.000 views per year
	Information requests	
	How many times it has been shared in Social Media	
Videos and multimedia	Number of views in Youtube and Social Media	-
Social Media Channels	LinkedIn: Impressions, clicks, followers	-
	Twitter: Interactions, community analysis of key publications	
Joint events and networking	Number of attendees	A total of at least 10 web-

	Type of audience	training sessions and 6 physical sessions
	Countries reached	
	Type of communication material shared	
Public Relations with Media	Media Clipping	-
General Communication materials	Poster, flyer, roll-up and brochure	-

6.2. Dissemination Performance Indicators

Participation in events: Regarding participation in events, at least 4 seminars per year on DATA CELLAR topics should be organised by POLITO, RUG, CERTH, LINKS. In addition, at least 3 specific PhD programmes should be prepared by POLITO, RUG, LINKS and a training programme including knowledge on due diligence and SDGs by ZABALA. A total of at least 10 web-based training sessions and 6 physical sessions will also be organised (1 more EU oriented in concomitance with final project event and 5 privileging VC areas and countries also to use native language).

Scientific publications: The industry partners are expected to publish between 7 and 10 scientific papers during the project. Preference will be given to the generation of publications related with the project activities and results, which will be mainly submitted for publication in international scientific journals with high impact and open as possible.

When tracking the impact of the Communication and Dissemination actions, the numbers will be considered, but also **how close we must come to our target audience**. The number of impacts is important, but the **quality of the actions** should be taken into account too. For example, it can be more interesting to have a committed DATA CELLAR community in social media that is engaged with the project and interacts with the accounts rather than a big number of followers that are not involved. Similarly, when choosing the impacts in media we want to have, it should be considered which is our objective where the audience want to reach.

6.3. Tracking tools

With the aim of evaluating and measuring the different actions, the following monitoring tools will be defined in the Communication Plan:

- **Google Analytics** is a powerful tool for monitoring the project’s website: it is useful to know mainly the origin and the time when the traffic reaches the DATA CELLAR website. It will also be used to prove if social media campaigns are achieving the goal to direct traffic to the website.

- **Google Alerts, Google organic research and the partners feedback** will give the project information about the news that have been published in media (press clipping), so that we can test the effectiveness of the press releases and networking.
- **Social Media Analytics** are essential to get to know the DATA CELLAR community and their behaviour towards the project. Each Social Media Channel has its own tracking system.

7. Management of communication

7.1. Communication team

Zabala Innovation is the leader of the WP8 about Communication and Dissemination activities. The actions and processes will be coordinated with RINA-C (leader of the project), and the rest of the members of the consortium through the Communication Team. This team consists of, at least, one member of each partner and the designated media representative (s) from each of the Communication/Marketing/Business Departments of every partner organisation. The main objectives of the Communication Team are to identify suitable opportunities to communicate about the DATA CELLAR project and to ensure that all communication material correctly reflects the R&D content of the project.

Designated media contact person(s) from each organisation is directly responsible for answering questions on communication issues, and for reviewing, commenting on, validating the communication material produced within the framework of DATA CELLAR. In addition, the media contact person is also responsible to ensure the internal validation of the content/material by its respective organisation, contacting the relevant internal technical team at their own criteria. It is also important to ensure smooth communication within their organisation about the project and its promotional activities.

DATA CELLAR partners play a key role in the execution of the Diss & Comm Plan as they represent the most important ambassadors and multipliers for the disseminating and communicating messages, achievements, and results towards stakeholders. All partners are required by the Grant Agreement to disseminate their generated results, and all are requested to contribute to communication and awareness raising activities.

The collaboration between the partners, the Communication team and Zabala Innovation is essential to ensure timely and accurate publication of project information on the project website and social media channels, as well as maximising the impact of the communication strategy and reaching the targeted audience.

7.2. External communication procedure

PRODUCTION OF DATA CELLAR COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

- At project level, Zabala Innovation is responsible for producing communication material such as press releases, general project presentation, project leaflets, website text, posters and banners, videos, contributions to social media discussions and similar material.
- Zabala Innovation will also source visual material, graphics, and logos from the DATA CELLAR partners.

- All material produced by Zabala Innovation will be in English. Zabala will also translate the materials into Spanish when is necessary. If any partner wants to translate relevant materials into the local language, they can do so.

REVIEW AND APPROVAL PROCEDURE

Zabala will initiate all approval procedures for communication material, either upon own initiative, or upon request from a consortium partner who would like his/her communication material approved. Moreover, Zabala Innovation will consult with the relevant partners on the content of the communication material in order to ensure the accuracy of the message.

1. Zabala Innovation sends out request for review and validation of general communication material by email to the Communication Team.
2. The Communication Team responds by email to Zabala within the fixed deadline (depending on the nature of the material) with specific comments (in track changes) and feedback on the proposed materials.
 - The designated media representatives will react to the proposed communication material according to the following deadlines:
 - Normal deadline: 10 working days. The normal deadline applies to general communication material.
 - Urgent consultation: 2 working days. The urgent procedure applies to press material, as well as in cases where urgent input on some specific type of short publications/articles is required. When urgent input is required, this should be clearly indicated by the person initiating the approval procedure (i.e. in the email subject).
3. Even in the case of no issues/comments, partners are kindly asked to respond to the request stating their approval and lack of comments.
4. If no feedback is given within the allocated time by any of the partners, it is assumed that no objections are raised by the respective partner.
5. Zabala Innovation consolidates feedback, resolves outstanding issues, finalises material for use and distributes it to all partners. Media representatives from each partner are responsible for local dissemination and translation if needed.

COMMUNICATION RESOURCES OF PROJECT PARTNERS

As planned in the proposal, the partners are encouraged to involve their marketing and communication departments in the Project Dissemination and Communication Plan: links from their organisation's website to the DATA CELLAR website, mentions in the accounts of Social Media Channels or translation of press releases.

In the case of the press releases the members of the consortium are asked to translate them into their local language and send them to Zabala Innovation, as well as the impact on the media to build the project's press clippings.

PRODUCTION OF COMMUNICATION MATERIAL IN CONNECTION WITH THE DATA CELLAR PROJECT BY THE PARTNERS:

- Partners of DATA CELLAR project may wish to publish information regarding DATA CELLAR in their own website, make presentations at relevant events and issue own press material that might contain information about the project.
- All material produced by project partners must follow the review and approval procedure described above and should follow the guidelines below.
- Project partners are asked to follow the corporate identity of DATA CELLAR, comprising both a written identity and a visual identity, making it compatible with the own partner corporate identity.
- Project partners should include in the communication produced the EU flag with the disclaimer.
- Project partners are asked to ensure the accuracy of the information.
- Whenever possible project should use available material previously approved.
- Partners are asked to send Zabala Innovation a copy of the published document and press clippings in order to keep track of all the dissemination activities.
- Project partners should provide their contact details at the end of their presentations, articles and press releases, but also present the Zabala Innovation contact details.

PRODUCTION OF SCIENTIFIC COMMUNICATION MATERIAL:

In order to ensure that the visual identity of the project is respected in scientific communication material and to make sure that there is no conflict between communication and partners' intellectual property rights, the partners willing to produce a scientific publication will have to follow the present procedure:

- The partner informs the rest of the Technical Committee.
- Once it has acceptance from the Technical Committee, the partner in charge of the publication sends RINA-C and Zabala Innovation the draft publication at least 20 working days before sending it for publication/10 working days if the partner was the only one involved in the research.
- Zabala Innovation circulates the document to all the partners that have participated to the research. Partners have 10 working days to send back their comments. If there is only one partner involved in the research, the partner just needs the approval of RINA-C and Zabala Innovation.
- After making sure that all the comments are considered that there is no conflict with partners' intellectual property rights and that the visual identity of the project is respected, RINA-C and Zabala Innovation give their approval to the partner for the publication.

7.3. Coordination with EC Communication Teams

DATA CELLAR will try to gain visibility and impact through the coordinator with the EC Communication teams. This coordination with the EC Communication channels related to Health and innovation will be carried out during key moments of the project such as the release of publication or celebration of important events.

The DATA CELLAR Communication Team will facilitate the interaction with the EC Communication teams by tagging them regularly in the published content.

7.4. Responsibilities

Zabala Innovation managed the purchase and hosting of the domain (www.datacellarproject.eu) and has designed and developed the website architecture and user experience. The graphic chart and web design are in line with the DATA CELLAR visual identity.

Regarding partners' responsibilities, the members of the consortium are requested to **identify communication opportunities and offer information that enables the creation of articles on the website**. Each of the partners must help provide complementary material (such as articles, pictures from the workshops and events, etc.) which can be later used for communication activities. This will be promoted by proposing a calendar of publications along with the partners.

The partners' collaboration is essential in the **creation of news pieces for the project website**. They are in direct contact with the project's progress and the ones most involved in the sector, aware of each news piece or publication that may affect them. For that reason, the Comm & Diss package leader should encourage the partner's participation in the news creation process. The following steps will be observed to involve the consortium in the Comm & Diss of the project through new pieces:

- Analysis of Comm & Diss opportunities

Zabala Innovation has analysed the communication opportunities of each WP and list them. Zabala has identified the milestone of each WP and has create a table to list the Comm & Diss opportunities of the WPs. (Table 5).

This has been done to provide the partners with **ideas about what can be accomplished**. The partners will be asked to complete or correct the information.

- Participation guidelines

An email will be sent to the partners to **explain how to collaborate** in the creation of news about the project.

How to help in news creation?

Zabala will prepare a Word template to fill in with information on the piece of news proposes to create. Partners will receive the template through emai, and they will have two weeks to complete it. Within two weeks, the news piece will be created and once it has finished, coordinators will have one week to revise it. When no answer are provided in the form of revisions, this will be considered a validation of the news piece.

As an example: X will publish in April. On the 1st of March Y will receive the email with the template, and Y will have to complete by the 15th. The news piece will be finalised by the end of the month and X will receive it back or correction during the first week of April.

Images which accompany the news document should be added when sending the information, in jpg. Or png. Format in a separate file.

The website will be actively promoted by all the partners on their website homepages, as well as on all their communication channels such as press releases or published articles.

Technical support and manteinance of the website will be carried out during the project's lifetime.

8. Horizon Europe request

The section outlines the procedures related with Dissemination and Communication as presented in the articles 16, 17, 21 and 26 of the Grant Agreement. Specific information related to the DATA CELLAR consortium and objectives following the EU legislation are presented.

As stated by the grant agreement obligations, **Article 17.2 “Visibility – European flag and funding statement”**, the support to DATA CELLAR project of the European Union must be clearly recognised in the dissemination and communication materials created within the project, including those developed by the partners. Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, it must follow the following rules:

- The symbol must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by additions such as patterns or text
- No other logo may be used to express the support by the European Union
- When displayed with other logos (e.g., partners’ or sponsors’ imagoypes), the EU flag must be as prominent and visible as the rest

Complying with **Article 17.3 “Quality of information – Disclaimer”** any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

Figure 18. Mandatory disclaimer

Fulfilling **Article 21.1 “Continuous reporting”**, similarly to all the partners, Zabala Innovation must continuously report on the actions and activities related to the Diss & Comm plan.

Finally, according to **Article 26.1 “Impact evaluation”**, the grant authority may carry out impact evaluations of the performance, measured against the objectives and indicators of the EU programme funding grant.

Obligations for Exploitation and IP

According to the **Article 16.1 “Background and access right to background”** beneficiaries must give each other, and other participants access to the background identified as needed for implementing the project actions. If background is subject to rights of a third party, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it is able to comply with its obligations under the Agreement.

According to **Article 16.2 “Protection of Results”** beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant must adequately protect their results.

Beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant must – up to four years after the end of the action – use their best efforts to exploit their results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing. If, despite a beneficiary’s best efforts, the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the action, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed in writing with the granting authority) use the Horizon Results Platform to find interested parties to exploit the results.

Additional Obligations: Where the call conditions impose additional exploitation obligations in case of a public emergency, the beneficiaries must (if requested by the granting authority) grant for a limited period of time specified in the request, non-exclusive licences – under fair and reasonable conditions – to their results to legal entities that need the results to address the public emergency and commit to rapidly and broadly exploit the resulting products and services at fair and reasonable conditions. This provision applies up to four years after the end of the action.

9. Planning

Actions	2022							2023													
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19		
Deliverables																					
WP8 deliverables				D8.1												D8.2					
Diss & Comm of other deliverables						D1.1										D2.3				D6.1 D6.2	
Social Media																					
Twitter & LinkedIn launching	x																				
Events Management		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Community Management		X	x	X	x	X	x	X	x	X	X	x	X	X	X	x	X	x	X	X	
Social Media Campaigns			X	x	X	x	X	x	X	x	x	X	x	X	x	X	x	X	X	x	
Website																					
Launching			x																		
Content update			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Comm materials																					
Logo and visual guidelines	x																				
Poster/roll up						x	x														
Templates	x																				
General brochure						x	x														

Launching																								
Content update	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Comm materials																								
Logo and visual guidelines																								
Poster/roll up																								
Templates																								
General brochure																								
Project video																								
Events and networking																								
Event tools and implementation																								
Networking	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Work with media																								
Data base of media																								
Press Releases								x					x					x						x

10. Conclusion

This document should be used as a roadmap to guide the communication actions surrounding the DATA CELLAR project. A communication plan is something that is written to define objectives and guide actions but it is the opposite of a static document. What this means is that it needs to be constantly updated.

The project evolves, as does its institutional environment, stakeholders and the actions of other actors. This is why it is important to be attentive through listening procedures, for example on social networks, in order to detect new trends or currents of interest that can help drive the project forward.

Moreover, thanks to the measurement procedures that will be carried out, it will be easy to see whether we are working in the right direction or whether we need to change it. And if we need to proceed, the numbers will show us where not to go and where to go. That is why it is so important to measure the impact that is achieved both in social networks, on the web and in media impacts.

Therefore, this is a first deliverable in which we have defined many actions and directions to work on during the first months, but which will have to be modified as the months go by in order to adapt to the environment and evolve in it.